

Production lines at Hanoi Plastic Company, supplier to Samsung Electronics. Courtesy by Tuan PM 2020

FINAL INCEPTION REPORT

SUPPLY CHAIN RESILIENCY DEEP DIVE IN SOUTHEAST ASIA

NOVEMBER 29, 2021

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DRAFT INCEPTION REPORT

SUPPLY CHAIN RESILIENCY DEEP DIVE IN SOUTHEAST ASIA

Contracted under

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United States Agency for International Development (USAID) /Regional Development Mission for Asia (RDMA)

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ACRONYM LIST

AMAF	ASEAN Ministers of Agriculture and Forestry
APT	ASEAN Plus Three
AQ	Assessment Question
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
AT	Assessment Team
CIEM	Central Institute of Economic Management
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease of 2019
DGICM	Divisions of the Ministries of Foreign Affairs
EQUI	Ensure Quality, Utilization, and Impact
ERIA	Economic Research Institute for ASEAN and East Asia.
EU	European Union
FY	Fiscal Year
GESI	Gender Equity and Social Inclusion
HILF	High-Impact-Low-Frequency
HQ	Headquarters
KII	Key Informant Interview
RDMA	Regional Development Mission for Asia
SCR	Supply Chain Resiliency
SEA	South-East Asia
SME	Small and Medium Size Enterprises
SEOM	Senior Economic Officials Meeting
SI	Social Impact, Inc.
SOM	Senior Officials Meeting
SOMHD	Senior Officials Meeting on Health Development
SOW	Scope of Work
STOM	Senior Transport Officials Meeting
TBD	To Be Determined
TL	Team Leader
US	United States
USAID	United States Agency for International Development

INTRODUCTION AND PURPOSE

This inception report summarizes the Assessment Team (AT)'s findings from the document review that address the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) Regional Development Mission for Asia (RDMA)'s requested Supply Chain Resiliency (SCR) Deep Dive assessment. In addition, the Inception Report lays out the AT's assessment design and methodologies for primary data collection to identify specific findings, conclusions, and recommendations with respect to RDMA's potential role in strengthening the resilience of Asia-Pacific regional supply chains.

CONTEXT

Southeast Asia (SEA) has been steadily moving towards greater regional integration since the late 1960s and each country within the region has positioned themselves as major players in the global economy. However, economic integration with global markets has had the side-effect of making the region one of the most vulnerable to the kinds of environmental, economic, and health-related shocks that create major disruptions in supply chains. In addition, SEA faces challenges, such as unsustainable debt levels, digital transformation needs, and collapsing supply and value chains. The recent coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has, also, exposed specific supply chain weaknesses, such as an overreliance on production in the People's Republic of China (PRC), that further impacts hard-hit economies, which increases exposure to shocks and further complicates economic recovery. These exposed supply-side vulnerabilities have been disproportionately affecting small and medium-sized enterprises, especially in Least Developed Countries in the region.¹

The types of workers at Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SME) might vary considerably across countries in SEA and sector. As a general note regarding sectors which rely on migrant labor, the COVID-19 pandemic has influenced most migration movements and corridors in the world, driving down migration. In Asia, migration corridors that are normally very active suddenly closed for several months. Origin and destination countries applied strict entry rules to control the pandemic within their borders. Deployment and outflows of migrant workers fell across the region, particularly during the first months of the pandemic² which raises questions about how border crossings will be handled in future situations.

Regional Development Objective 2 (RDO2) of the USAID/RDMA's Regional Development Cooperation Strategy (RDCS) for Asia (2020–2025) addresses these supply vulnerabilities by strengthening regional supply chains to become more resilient to unanticipated, long-term shocks, like COVID-19.³ RDO 2 will “promote and institutionalize principles of transparency, public accountability, environmental responsibility, and gender equality and inclusive development to fortify the integrity of economic connectivity.”⁴

PURPOSE

The SCR Deep Dive will provide data for evidence-based decision making and identify possible approaches to inform activity design that benefit future RDMA programming. The impacts and

¹ Excerpted from USAID Deep Dive SCR SOW

² UN Women. (2020). The Impact of COVID-19 on Women. Available at: <https://www.unwomen.org/-/media/headquarters/attachments/sections/library/publications/2020/policy-brief-the-impact-of-covid-19-on-women-en.pdf?la=en&vs=1406>.

³ (USAID). 2020. Regional Development Cooperation Strategy (RDCS). December 2020 – December 2025. Available at: <https://www.usaid.gov/asia-regional/rdc>

⁴ Ibid

opportunities presented by the COVID-19 pandemic will be integrated into report findings that tests the logic of RDMA's Regional Development Cooperation Strategy's (RDCS) theory of change: "IF RDMA supports policy development and advocacy efforts that a) support private sector efforts to promote supply chain resiliency, and b) reduce barriers to using open platforms for knowledge-sharing and network strengthening, Then RDMA can effectively help supply chains in the region be more resilient to unanticipated, long-term shocks."

The SCR Deep Dive calls for the completion of two interconnected tasks: 1) An analysis of data and information on priority entry points, including policymaking bodies and private sector networks around vulnerabilities among regional supply chains; and 2) The co-development of an information dissemination workshop that includes recommendations for programmatic approaches to work with public and private platforms to advance supply chain resiliency at a regional level.

Ultimately, USAID/RDMA seeks to identify models, potential partners, and opportunities for collaboration that will help it develop future programming that is geared towards helping SEA public and private sector actors who are keen to enhance their SCR.

UNDERSTANDING OF THE SCOPE OF WORK

The SCR Deep Dive examines four assessment questions (AQs) and sub-questions. These, along with explanations for how the team plan to address each, are listed below.

- AQ 1: What are the main challenges to regional SCR in SEA given ongoing and probable future shocks in SEA?
 - The AT will identify the main challenges that are expected to impact SCR in SEA - now and in the future.
- AQ 2: What public and private actors are working regionally to identify and mitigate SCR risks and vulnerabilities?
 - The AT will identify organizations that are working regionally on identifying and managing the potential (risk) shocks or disruptions, and/or working to minimize the impact or likelihood that the risks will become a reality.
- AQ 2a: Which economic sectors offer the best opportunities to bolster regional SCR in SEA in a way that can serve as a model for other sectors?
 - The answer to this question will provide a systematic analysis of economic sectors that offer the greatest potential for facilitating SCR in SEA and for helping the AT identify possible opportunities and models of SCR.
- AQ 2b: How can these actors be supported?
 - This question seeks to understand and define the needs of these organizations working on supply chain vulnerabilities and how USAID can help them.
- AQ 3: What are the potential frameworks USAID could employ to develop a regional early warning system that could help identify SCR risks that could help reduce the impact of supply chain disruptions?
 - This question seeks to identify and develop a set of parameters that can be used to design an early warning system for anticipating and managing supply chain risks that will reduce the impact of supply chain disruptions or shocks throughout the region.

KEY ASSESSMENT DEFINITIONS

SUPPLY CHAIN RESILIENCE (SCR)

There are many definitions of SCR that include aspects such as “unforeseeable, sudden, unpredictable, low frequency/high impact, low certainty,” of events happening along with the supply chain’s capacity to quickly respond and restore itself. The definition offered below does not distinguish between what is foreseeable or not and looks at SCR as part of an overall state of readiness that seeks to maintain the smooth operations of supply chains. Based on this, the AT’s working definition of SCR is:

“The ability of supply chains to withstand the impact of any type of disruption and quickly return to the original or a better level of operations.”

This definition has three parts:

- Anticipation, which covers the parameters of visibility, awareness, security, sustainability, and supply chain risk management.
- Resistance, which covers the parameters of flexibility, redundancy, collaboration, supply chain network, revenue sharing, robustness.
- Recovery and response, which includes parameters such as velocity, agility, public-private partnerships, adaptability, market position, and info sharing, which can be considered part of resilience capacity.⁵

SUPPLY CHAIN RESILIENCE (SCR) CAPACITY

The AT will use the following definition:

“Capacity that should be designed to cope with all risks of disruption that differ in frequency, severity, impact, duration and recovery time.”

There are two risk categories: 1) Low-Impact-High-Frequency risks, which cover operational matters such as poor coordination among supply chain entities and are evident in supply and demand disparity, machine breakdowns, power outages, demand fluctuations. and uncertainties in lead times.; and 2) High-Impact-Low-Frequency (HILF) risks, which covers uncertainties in lead times which pertain to natural hazards, terrorism, and political instability which have severe long-term economic/social consequences and entail long recovery periods. There are also HILF risks for single and multiple sourcing in the presence of disruption risks.⁶

Some examples of resilience mechanisms that address the two risk categories mentioned above include: a) risk mitigation inventories; b) subcontracting capacities; c) backup supply; d) transportation infrastructures; e) omnichannel distribution systems; f) flexible production technologies; and g) data driven, real time, monitoring and visibility systems. These mechanisms are potential solutions for managing the risks and ties in with the SCR capacity definition. To build SCR capacity, firms and other actors need to take measures or implement solutions like those listed in this part.

A model that addresses SCR capacity is used to present the **complexity of relationships** where the same firm can be both supplier and buyer and "frenemies" (e.g., Samsung and Apple). The model uses ideas from ecology (i.e., trophic chains pyramids), where market demand is at the top, then focal firms in the middle and many suppliers at the base. The model is applied to understand a) risk propagation,

⁵ Ivanov and Dolgui. (2020). Viability of intertwined supply networks: extending the supply chain resilience angles towards survivability. A position paper motivated by COVID-19 outbreak. International Journal of Production Research, Volume 58, 2020 - Issue 10. Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00207543.2020.1750727>.

⁶ Namdar et. al. (2018). Supply chain resilience for single and multiple sourcing in the presence of disruption risks. International Journal of Production Research, Volume 56, 2018, Issue 6, pg. 3-8. Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00207543.2017.1370149>.

b) quality management and control, c) circular economy, d) competition modelling, and e) digital twinning of supply chains, which are computerized supply chain models that represent the network state for any given moment in real time.⁷ This model proposes a system for enhancing SCR resilience in the context where companies can cooperate and compete at the same time.

SHOCKS AND VULNERABILITIES

Shocks are defined as the realization of highly unexpected events that cause losses.

Vulnerabilities in this context refers to an exposure to serious disturbance, arising from risks within the supply chain as well as risks external to the supply chain and the weak ability of many sectors/organizations to withstand these disruptions.

SHORT-TERM AND LONG-TERM OPPORTUNITIES

Short-term opportunities are immediate and continuing with the possibility for a fast response with quick impacts, for example:

- Expansion of the China Plus+I Model⁸ due to high labor costs in China
- Tariff wars
- Japan providing incentives for regionalization in SEA
- Vietnam benefited from taking up textiles, footwear, and electronic industries.⁹
- Price optimization and supplier standardization through safety and quality

Immediate and Short-term opportunities are from the present to the end of year 4 and could include proposals and interventions that build on existing reform efforts in sectors that have demonstrable SCR interventions that are visible, accountable, and measurable

Long Term opportunities are possible benefits of regional free trade agreements such as Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP), which includes all major Asian countries. Free trade agreements will, eventually, reduce transaction costs when utilized to the fullest extent possible. Large companies are likely to stay active within this bloc. Advanced industries comprise Thailand's electric vehicle hub and Malaysia's solar cell module production cluster.¹⁰

Long term opportunities are those arising beyond 10 years and could be related to developing new platforms for long term policy options in sectors best monitored and governed for SCR with highest impacts.

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS AND GAPS FROM THE DESK REVIEW

This section highlights the AT's findings from the desk review and gaps in information that the AT will endeavor to fill through primary data collection. Initial findings and information gaps from the document review are presented below by AQ. The findings identified in this report are preliminary;

⁷ Ivanov and Dolgui. (2020). Viability of intertwined supply networks.

⁸ Insight Team. (2021). What is the China Plus One Strategy, and What Should You Know About It? Available at: <https://insight-quality.com/china-plus-one-strategy/>.

⁹ Maude. (2021). Trading Out of Trouble – Southeast Asia's Trade Prospects in a COVID-19 World. Asia Society Policy Institute. Available at: <https://southeastasiacovid.asiasociety.org/trading-out-of-trouble-southeast-asias-trade-prospects-in-a-covid-19-world/>.

¹⁰ Ibid.

the AT will triangulate them with information provided by stakeholders during the data collection phase of the assessment to crosscheck results.

AQ I. WHAT ARE THE MAIN CHALLENGES TO REGIONAL SCR IN SEA GIVEN ONGOING AND PROBABLE FUTURE SHOCKS IN SEA?

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

The following is an initial list of challenges that are anticipated to produce probable future shocks that were identified for their disproportionately high impact on SEA.⁸

- Climate change readiness is weak in SEA with several countries already in precarious positions because of climate change.
- Natural disasters are coming with increasing intensity and frequency.
- The region is prone to natural disasters and flooding with severe floods and storms that occur regularly and thus, continually affect the region and produce economic damage that can be expected. Flooding in SEA has been made worse by landfills, dredging of rivers, and deforestation.
- Weak inclusion of marginalized people (e.g., smallholders, women, youth, refugees, and conflict-affected people) involved in supply chains, which leads to greater dislocations and hardships when crises arise.
- Disrupted transport/trade linkages and flows from material shortages, which arise from economic, political, and environmental crises.
- COVID-19 restrictions on workers and transport blockages, which lead to shortages of truck drivers and containers, overstretched ports that collectively affect the region, and downstream markets in the United States (US) and elsewhere; similar challenges are expected with future pandemics.
- Reduced supply chain visibility, defined as the ability to track parts, components, and/or products from the manufacturer to their final destination.
- Over reliance on China for intermediate inputs locks the region into limited scope to maneuver in the event of a disruption.
- Long delays with finding intermediate suppliers causes further delays with production of finished products.
- Time consuming and costly process of supplier diversification that result because of difficulties finding suitable suppliers and ramping up production and logistics with the new suppliers.
- Supply chain has no governance structure above the firm level but is a loose market regulated system which has to face interventions which may be seen as market disruption.
- Less valued risk management culture in Asia across suppliers.
- More recent supply chain relationships that have developed are often viewed as commodity-like and interchangeable, rather than as long-term partnerships resulting in a limited risk management infrastructure.
- There is a need to distinguish between once in a lifetime risk and those that may be equally unpredictable, but potentially more frequent, which will require different levels of emergency and contingency planning.
- Lack of necessary transport and energy infrastructure to sustain supply chains.¹¹ Production and logistics depend on the adequate numbers of ports, airports, and roads that can handle containers, bulk materials, and other highly traded commodities and connect materials and people to each node along the supply chain.

¹¹ ADB estimates that ASEAN will need infrastructure investments of \$60 billion annually mostly for transport and energy. Contaminated water and water shortages affect supply chains that rely on reliable, adequate water supply.

- Lack of good quality water supplies and clash of competing economic interests for water supplies.¹²
- Over dependence on fossil fuels.¹³
- Insecure energy supplies.¹⁴
- Imposition of non-tariff Measures/non-tariff barriers by the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) member states such as export bans of personal protective equipment (PPE) but applies to other areas of trade facilitation such as complex/unnecessary customs clearance procedures.
- Actual and potential terrorist attacks that disrupt supply chains.
- Geopolitical and domestic political risks that disrupt supply chains such as military coups in Thailand, fallout from the crisis in Myanmar, tensions in the Persian Gulf that interrupt oil supplies, potential conflict between China and Taiwan.
- Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) issues owned by exclusive supplier of emergency items such as medical goods and other items that would be deemed crucial by member states for reducing the impact of disasters. IPR to these products may have to be waived and will face resistance.
- Trade contraction.

INFORMATION GAPS

- The list of challenges needs to be confirmed with key government and private sector stakeholders.
- Additional challenges will be identified during the fieldwork.
- Challenges should be ranked or prioritized by stakeholders based on perceptions of the most pressing challenges.

AQ 2. WHAT PUBLIC AND PRIVATE ACTORS ARE WORKING REGIONALLY TO IDENTIFY AND MITIGATE SCR RISKS AND VULNERABILITIES?

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

- Potential regional actors working on SCR risks and vulnerabilities: a potential regional network for enhancing SCR could be based on the following findings/conclusions from the ASEAN Plus Three (APT) study.
 - Digital supply chains are gaining greater traction with economic contractions and reduced orders.
 - Suppliers are entering new markets, while adjusting inventories and diversifying sales channels.
 - Most respondents in the APT study do not plan to relocate and bringing back production to home countries is not seen as an immediate possibility.¹⁵
- The concept of Supply Chain Connectivity (SCC) involves a possible regional network with the purpose of:
 - Enhancing integration and improving communications and coordination.

¹² Examples of rice cultivation competing with other crops or industries, e.g., semiconductors, electronics, data centers, textiles, etc. that all require plentiful water supplies.

¹³ Many key ASEAN economies have become net energy importers and energy diversification remain slow; SEA was formerly a net exporter of oil and gas, IEA projects will rise to \$300 billion by 2040, driven by importing oil and, to a lesser extent, gas.

¹⁴ IEA definition of energy security is uninterrupted access to energy at an affordable price. SEA will have greater difficulty adjusting to volatile prices and supply shortages without impairing SC operations.

¹⁵ ERIA. (2020). Joint Study on I0+3 Cooperation for Improvement of Supply Chain Connectivity: ASEAN Sub-Report.

Available at: <https://www.eria.org/uploads/media/Research-Project-Report/Joint-Study-on-I0%2B3-Cooperation-for-Improvement-of-Supply-Chain-Connectivity.pdf>.

- Focusing on weak links in infrastructure to improve border transport connectivity.
- Strengthening regulatory coordination and cooperation to establish standards and rules.
- Leveraging free trade agreements to guarantee supply chains.
- Developing new infrastructure, specifically, for digital tools (e.g., digital customs clearance, Rules of Origin etc.).
- Encouraging technology sharing and capacity building for SCC.¹⁶
- Initiatives from the ASEAN Economic Community and the Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity Include:
 - Strengthening ASEAN ability to address SCR by collaborating with the following bodies:
 - Senior Economic Officials Meeting (SEOM)
 - Senior Transport Officials Meeting (STOM)
 - Directors General of Immigration Departments and Heads of Consular Affairs
 - Divisions of the Ministries of Foreign Affairs (DGICM)
 - Senior Officials Meeting on Health Development (SOMHD)
 - Customs Directors General (DGs)
 - Senior Officials Meeting for ASEAN Ministers on Agriculture and Forestry (SOM-AMAF)
 - Logistics and Transport Services Sectoral Working Group (LTSSWG).
 - These connections will/could enhance supply chain efficiency by addressing key chokepoints for SEOM, STOM, customs DGs, DGICM; SOMHD, SOM-AMAF, LTSSWG, and Logistics coordinating councils¹⁷
- The following **public sector/government** institutions were identified during the desk review as active in SCR matters:¹⁸
 - Director IV, Central Management, Office of Department of Finance, Philippines.
 - Agency of Enterprise Development under Ministry of Planning and Investment (Vietnam).
 - Central Institute of Economic Management (CIEM, Vietnam).
 - Vietrade.
 - Ministry of Agriculture and Development (Agro Processing and Market Development Authority), Vietnam.
 - Trade Consulate of the Vietnam Embassy in Singapore..
- The following **private sector organizations/networks** were identified during the desk review as being active in SCR matters:
 - Lead firms such as Samsung, Canon, and Toyota: Example of "How Toyota strengthened its supply chain".¹⁹
 - Logistics Inland Container Depot (ICD) at Vinh Phuc (Vietnam), a joint venture between Technology & Trade (T&T) Vietnam; YCH Holdings (Singapore) and YCH Group Pte Ltd.
 - This is based on the Supply Chain City in Singapore to connect Vietnam with the south China market.²⁰

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ ASEAN Secretariat, Jakarta. (2017). Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025, pg. 92. Available at: <https://asean.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/47.-December-2017-MPAC2025-2nd-Reprint-.pdf>

¹⁸ AUS4Reform. (2021). Making Economic Recovery and Institutional Reforms Intertwined after COVID-19. Available at: <http://aus4reform.org.vn/en/Library/Economic-Restructuring-and-Business-Enabling-Environment/making-economic-recovery-and-institutional-reforms-intertwined-after-covid-19-way-forward-for-vietnam-438099/>; Vietnam Trade Promotion Agency. (2021). Vietnam - Singapore cooperate to jointly develop exports to EU and UK. Available at: <http://www.vietrade.gov.vn/>

¹⁹ Lund et. al. (2020). Risk, resilience, and rebalancing in global value chains. McKinsey & Company, pg. 80. Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/operations/our-insights/risk-resilience-and-rebalancing-in-global-value-chains>.

²⁰ Datur. (2021). Approving the investment project of Vinh Phuc ICD logistics center worth 3,878 billion VND. Available at: <https://baodautu.vn/phe-duyet-du-an-dau-tu-trung-tam-logistics-icd-vinh-phuc-tri-gia-3878-ty-dong-d133100.html>.

- Others: DHL Express, UPS, Google, R3, and Next trade Group.²¹
- The following **academic institutions** were identified:²²
 - Economic Research Institute for ASEAN and East Asia
 - VoxEU (Research-based policy analysis and commentary from leading economists)

INFORMATION GAPS

- Initial desk review does not shed major insights into supply chain management at the regional level.
- No real initiative/intervention has been revealed about regional supply chain hubs.

AQ 2A. WHICH ECONOMIC SECTORS OFFER THE BEST OPPORTUNITIES TO BOLSTER REGIONAL SCR IN SEA IN A WAY THAT CAN SERVE AS A MODEL FOR OTHER SECTORS?

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

- The AT has developed the following selection process for identifying priority sectors:
 - Preparing a long list of the largest sectors (10) of imports and exports between ASEAN and US/European Union (EU), Australia, India, Japan, South Korea and China.
 - Ranking the long list of sectors by respective shares of ASEAN's total exports and imports with the US/EU, Australia, India, Japan, South Korea and China.
 - Filtering out the sectors based on share of employment in SEA economy.
 - Re-ranking the sectors based on the highest value measured in trade with an emphasis on SEA/ ASEAN exports and leading employment economic sectors and concentration in the middle- and low-income countries of Lower Mekong (CLM+V).
 - Evaluating the ranked sectors' best practices in developing SCR.
 - Preparing a short list of sectors that could be good models for regional SCR, and other emerging issues e.g., USAID priorities.
- Proposed economic sectors based on desk review:
 - Strategic sectors are based on geopolitics: 40 percent of Americans claim that they won't "buy in China"²³, therefore, techno-digital supply chains (e.g., semi-conductors) are to be diversified away from China. Supporting industries (e.g., transport and logistics) are vulnerable during shocks, especially, when impeded by political forces (e.g., trade wars). Essential security related sectors, e.g., food security and medical equipment/PPE may mandate reserve/quotas at the national level.²⁴ These strategic sectors include, for example, semiconductors,, transport and logistics, food/agriculture, and healthcare/medical products.

²¹ United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific (ESCAP). (2020). Digital Acceleration Dialogue: Enabling MSME E-commerce in Southeast and South Asia. Available at: <https://www.allianceforetradedevelopment.org/escap-digital-dialogue>.

²² Kimura. (2020). Exit Strategies for ASEAN Member States: Keeping Production Networks Alive Despite the Impending Demand Shock. ERIA. Available at: <https://www.eria.org/uploads/media/policy-brief/Exit-Strategies-For-AMS-Keeping-Production-Networks-Alive-Despite-The-Impending-Demand-Shock.pdf>.

²³ Fukuoka. (2020). Supply chain transformation underway in Southeast Asia—production shift due to US-China conflict and strengthened Resilience in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Asia, China & Oceania Dept., Global Economics & Political Studies Div. Mitsui & Co. Global Strategic Studies Institute. Available at: https://www.mitsui.com/mgssi/en/report/detail/_icsFiles/afieldfile/2020/09/18/2008c_fukuoka_e.pdf.

²⁴ For example, Singapore has 30% food security by 2030 but on limited essential food supplies.

- SEA offers opportunities based on human resource capability/cost, regulatory business environment/political stability, liberalization policies; options for redundancy with China+1²⁵; and integration of manufacturing and logistics sectors with visible, digital supply chains where product flow can be visualized.
- The possible economic sectors include the following:
 - Advanced industries such as automotive and electronics facing raw-material shortages from tier-2²⁶ companies that could benefit from greater transparency.
 - Customer-facing companies in tourism and hospitality, fragrances, business casual apparel dealing with decreased demand on discretionary goods.
 - Labor-intensive industries such as textiles/apparel, agriculture/food processing that are suffering the most from worker shortages.
 - China's domestic market with strong imports for integrated circuits, consumer electronics, palm oil and rubber.
 - Infrastructure investments across SEA.²⁷
- The following other sectors have been, specifically, proposed by the US Embassy to the Royal Thai Government:²⁸
 - Electronics and Components
 - Energy
 - Logistics and Transportation
 - Digital Economy
 - Medical
 - Food and Agriculture
 - Biotechnology

INFORMATION GAPS

- Supply chain responses are very company, sector, and country specific rather than high level regionally oriented.
- Most of the shocks experienced before were from natural disasters and responses have been driven by lead firms such as Samsung, Canon, Toyota, and the other major automotive Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs).

AQ 2B. HOW CAN THESE ACTORS BE SUPPORTED?

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

- Empower joint ASEAN approaches to issues concerning the food, agriculture, and forestry sectors as per the ASEAN Vision 2025, which calls for increased resilience to climate change, natural

²⁵ Not all or nothing approach, in practice policies that were considered during US-China trade war 2018 are being ramped up and taken more seriously. Flexport. A Field Guide to Southeast Asia supply chain options.

²⁶ Tier 2 companies are the suppliers who provide inputs to the major original equipment producers. An example would be supplies of interiors for Ford

²⁷ Chenneveau et. al (2020). A resilient return for Asia's manufacturing and supply chains? McKinsey and Company. Available at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/operations/our-insights/a-resilient-return-for-asias-manufacturing-and-supply-chains>.

²⁸ Suggested US Supply Chain and Investment Measures - June 12 Final

disasters, and other shocks.²⁹ Members states are all facing common challenges as articulated in ASEAN Vision 2025 and need ASEAN led solutions to strengthen bilateral approaches.

- Strengthen the voice of smallholders regionally to address supply chain issues³⁰ (trade associations, ASEAN committees/working groups). Smallholders are not represented at the regional level, so their interests are not being addressed.³¹
- Ensure that Agriculture ministries in the region are included in SCR dialogue platforms.³² National agriculture ministries have not been included in dialogue platforms for major upheavals (e.g., COVID-19 response) and they must be part of the dialogue to ensure that food supply chains are not disrupted.
- Collaborate with sector-based organizations and ASEAN committees/working groups to improve emergency planning at company and government levels. Most companies/governments are missing emergency and response planning processes - Business Continuity planning with the PDCA (plan, do, check, act) cycle.³³ Encourage ASEAN member states to establish a ministry of national resilience or disaster management as these do not exist on the national level³⁴ and are needed to coordinate plans and strategies for managing and responding to supply chain disruptions.

INFORMATION GAPS

- Identification of organizations operating in SEA that are demonstrating best practices in SCR capacity is challenging but vital as these would be champions that could spearhead regional SCR efforts; thus, it's difficult to obtain a clear picture regarding support needed to achieve best practices without having this information to use as a benchmark that would enable gap analysis.
- Limited information about actual actions/interventions by the regional platforms to ease the supply chain constraints in SEA, at least during the recent COVID-19 crisis.
- Lack of clear indications about support needed and by which organizations.

AQ 3. WHAT ARE THE POTENTIAL FRAMEWORKS USAID COULD EMPLOY TO DEVELOP A REGIONAL EARLY WARNING SYSTEM THAT COULD HELP IDENTIFY SCR RISKS THAT COULD HELP REDUCE THE IMPACT OF SUPPLY CHAIN DISRUPTIONS?

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

- A framework has been proposed using 17 indicators such as: agility, flexibility, robustness, visibility, IT capability/information sharing, collaboration, sustainability, awareness/sensitiveness, supply chain risk management culture (SCRM), velocity, market position, risk control/revenue sharing, public-private partnerships, adaptability, supply chain network, and security.

²⁹ Fan et. al. (2021). Food system resilience and COVID-19 – Lessons from the Asian experience. *Global Food Security*, Volume 28, March 2021, 100501, pg. 3. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211912421000110>.

³⁰ Minimal COVID-19 support for small holders

³¹ Fan et. al. (2021). Food system resilience, pg. 5

³² Ibid.

³³ ERIA. (2016). Oil Supply Resilience in ASEAN. Research Project Report 2016, No. 03, pg. 11. Available at: https://www.eria.org/RPR_FY2016_03.pdf.

³⁴ Ibid, pg. 40.

- This framework allocates the most important of the 17 indicators above to three different stages/phases of SCR: anticipation, resistance, and response/recovery to disruptions/shocks.³⁵
- The framework can, perhaps, be modified to focus on various stages/phases that can create an early warning system.

INFORMATION GAPS

- Getting a clear understanding about how companies/sectors currently measure resilience.
- Finding viable measurement models or frameworks that operate beyond the company level that could be the most inclusive of stakeholders including, possibly, marginalized groups.
- Determining the applicability of company level frameworks to the sector/country/regional level SCR context that might include women, youth, and persons with disabilities.

DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

DATA COLLECTION METHODS

The AT will use two types of data collection methods: 1) desk review and 2) key informant interviews (KIIs). The desk review and KIIs are mutually reinforcing in that the former provides preliminary findings that answer the AQs and identifies potential stakeholders, while the KIIs will also answer the AQs and those responses may either confirm or refute preliminary findings, offer new ideas, and recommend additional contacts who can be, subsequently, interviewed as KIIs. The AT will rely on KIIs to pose fairly broad questions to individuals who are active in SEA supply chains rather than with other methods (e.g., surveys), which often have low response rates, might not provide relevant information and are not feasible given current level of resources. The AT also considered focus group discussions and deemed them unfeasible due to challenges ensuring participants have the same relative positions within their respective organizations. As with surveys, focus group discussions would be very challenging to complete within the tight fieldwork timeframe, especially given the large number of potential KIIs. The AT will continue the desk review to follow up on suggested ideas and corroborate information learned during the KIIs.

DESK REVIEW

The AT commenced data collection with a comprehensive review of the available literature with a focus on supply chain resilience (SCR) that addresses the AQs. The AT reviewed and analyzed a wide range of sources including technical journals, reports, event summaries, and magazines authored by academics, government ministries, multilateral organizations, trade associations, and industry experts³⁶ to examine SCR in the context of SEA. Please see **Annex 2** for a list of documents reviewed during the desk review.

Previous SCR research enabled the AT to gain a clearer understanding of the issues relevant to SEA

³⁵ Singh and Badhotiya. (2019). Performance indicators for supply chain resilience: review and conceptual framework. *Journal of Industrial Engineering International* (2019) 15 (Suppl 1), page 107. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/334781594_Performance_indicators_for_supply_chain_resilience_review_and_conceptual_framework.

³⁶ Some examples include: Economic Research Institute of ASEAN and East Asia; Asia Pacific White Paper Series; Elsevier Computers & Industrial Engineering Journal; Journal of Industrial Engineering International; Harvard Business Review; Asia Business Council; Business Process Management Journal; Supply Chain and Logistics Journal; ASEAN Secretariat; Institute of Logistics and Warehousing and others.

to identify initial findings relevant to the AQs outlined in Section V. In addition, the AT identified a list of possible key informants and relevant organizations that may be able to inform this assessment. The team also used the desk review to identify definitions for terms critical to this assessment.

The team will likely discover new information as it engages directly with key informants; thus, the AT will augment new information collected from KIIs with additional document review as new documents are identified.

KEY INFORMANT INTERVIEWS (KIIS)

The AT will use a semi-structured KII questionnaire to collect information about the following: 1) all AQs and 2) new SCR ideas that are mentioned during the KIIs. The list of KIIs is comprised of 95 companies, associations, government ministries/agencies, universities, and think tanks who have been selected based on their current functions and roles related to trade, SCR, and key economic sectors in SEA that are also relevant to USAID/RDMA's RDCS. The AT will leverage existing relationships among these 95 possible key informants to gain access to other potential participants. In addition, KIIs may suggest other possible organizations for interviews. Please see **Annex 3** for the illustrative list of key stakeholders for more details. After the AT's analysis of completed KIIs, they might schedule follow up emails and calls to address any gaps and/or obtain more details. Out of the 95 potential KIIs, the AT plans to complete approximately 70 to 78 online interviews using two teams of two persons each over a 13-day period.

SAMPLING

The AT identified 95 organizations that have the most relevance, interest, and influence on supply chains in SEA as described in Table I below. While the AT intends to interview as many KIIs as possible, the team may not be able to identify contacts for all 95 organizations it has already identified and/or it may be difficult to schedule interviews with some individuals. Therefore, from the list of 95 organizations, the team expects to complete a minimum of 78 KIIs over the 13-day allocated for field research with two teams of two persons per team. The AT will also use snowball sampling to obtain referrals during KIIs to gather contact information for some of the organizations already identified as well as about additional possible relevant respondents. The AT will use snowball sampling to try and identify, for example, associations that represent marginalized groups in SEA.

The list 95 organizations the AT has already identified is comprised of relevant players in SEA's private sector supply chains and networks from the public and private sectors including umbrella associations, civil society organizations (CSOs), academia, regulators, policy makers and companies based upon the desk review and the team's sector expertise. Since this assessment focuses on regional SCR and SMEs, for the minimum sample of 78, the AT has prioritized private sector KIIs at the ASEAN level (e.g., ASEAN Secretariat Divisions, ASEAN Sector Working Groups, ASEAN Connectivity Initiatives, and trade/SME government promotion agencies), which account for 23 KIIs; the second largest group of KIIs are private sector companies in sectors such as healthcare, logistics, agriculture/food, hospitality, insurance, and port authorities which account for 22 KIIs. Business councils/associations, academia, chambers of commerce, collectively, account for 20 targeted KIIs, which is the third largest sub-sample selected during the desk review, based on their roles covering broad economic sectors and SCR and the academia, development partners, and international development agencies accounting for the remaining 13 KIIs. The team selected economic sectors within the private sector group of KIIs because they have been the most adversely impacted by COVID-19 and other supply chain disruptions and/or are engaged in SCR approaches identified during desk research. Table I below describes the total and targeted samples of KIIs as follows:

Table 1: Stakeholder Categories

Stakeholder Categories	Total Sample	Targeted Sample
Business Councils/ Associations	9	9
Academia / Thinktanks	7	5
Bi-lateral Chambers of Commerce	8	6
National / Federal Chambers of Commerce	4	4
US Associations	1	1
Agriculture/Food	3	2
Health Sector (incl. PPE, Medical Devices)	2	2
Hospitality and Tourism Sector	2	1
Logistics/ Shipping companies	3	3
Port Authorities	3	2
Tech firms (Infrastructure, Services)	2	2
Trade Finance/ Banks	2	1
Insurance	1	1
Multinational Lead Firms in SE Asia	7	5
Large Asian firms SE Asia	3	3
Regional Consulting Firms in SCR	2	0
Media	2	0
Development Partners-Group	3	2
ASEAN + Three (China+ Korea + Japan Missions to ASEAN)	1	1
International Development Missions	7	5
ASEAN Secretariat Divisions	6	6
ASEAN Sectoral Working Groups	3	3

Stakeholder Categories	Total Sample	Targeted Sample
Initiatives Under the Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025	8	8
Government Trade and SME Promotion Agencies in SE Asia	6	6
Total	95	78

DATA ANALYSIS

The team will take detailed notes of all KIs, which they will clean and share electronically on a rolling basis throughout the fieldwork. The AT will conduct internal debriefs at least every two days during fieldwork to discuss progress and make any needed adjustments in the schedule. The AT will discuss evidence collected to help answer the AOs as well as identify any discrepancies and/or gaps. The team will also begin identifying any emerging themes that may be helpful in developing the analysis framework.

During the data analysis process, the AT will use a tally sheet matrix, which will include themes that arise from the KIs and tally the number of times each theme occurs in the interviews, by stakeholder group, geographic area, and sex. This will enable the AT to look for trends within and across stakeholder groups, including trends by sex and geography.

The AT will utilize several data analysis methods to identify key findings from the collected data and to draw conclusions to answer the AOs. The type of analyses will depend on the specific questions being addressed (e.g., content analysis). Likely analysis methods will include the following:

- **Content and Thematic Analyses:** Content analysis will entail the AT’s intensive review of KIs transcripts to identify and highlight the existence of certain patterns and their frequencies, within the data. The data can then be summarized to better understand the importance of various economic sectors, the main challenges and issues/themes, best practices/models of SCR, frameworks, and the needs of various private and public sector actors.
- **Comparative Analysis:** The AT will compare, and contrast data collected within and across stakeholder groups and data sources to assess convergence and divergence in viewpoints.
- **GESI Analysis:** The AT will examine the impact of supply chain disruptions on marginalized groups in SEA by examining relevant data to draw conclusions related to each AO. All data collected through KIs will be disaggregated by sex and analyzed for effects on both male and female participants to assess any significant differences.

The team leader (TL) will oversee and manage systematic data analysis. The AT will compare data from the varied streams described above to determine whether findings are divergent or convergent. The extent to which multiple information streams provide consistent findings will inform the validity of assessment conclusions. Should the different sources diverge, the team will undertake additional analysis, and conclusions will be stated in a way that reflects the nuanced data. The AT will ensure that a large portion of data collected across all methods will address the same questions to enhance the possibilities of triangulation.

The AT will capture findings, conclusions, and recommendations (FCR) in an Excel-based matrix that categorizes analysis by AQ. The matrix: a) ensures that the AT prepares a systematic and thorough response to each AQ, b) verifies that analysis accounts for gender dimensions, c) identifies any gaps where additional clarification or analysis may be necessary, and d) serves as the basis for developing the assessment report.

DISSEMINATION AND UTILIZATION

In its commitment to foster study utilization, the AT has and will integrate dissemination and consultations throughout the study process. This includes:

START UP

The AT shared preliminary findings from the desk review with USAID. Likewise, revised AQs, definitions for important terms, and the study design, work plan, potential key informants, and tools were agreed upon through a consultation process.

IMPLEMENTATION

The AT will continue having regular check-ins throughout the study and weekly during data collection, in writing or meetings, as per USAID and the AT's availability and preference.

PRELIMINARY FINDINGS PRESENTATION

After data collection ends, the AT will virtually present an out brief to USAID/RDMA through a PowerPoint deck, which will cover preliminary findings and themes that emerged during data collection, alongside preliminary conclusions, and initial recommendations.

INFORMATION DISSEMINATION WORKSHOP

After the Out-brief presentation, the AT will facilitate a workshop with expected assessment users, notably USAID/RDMA, USAID/Washington, USAID bilateral Asia Missions, relevant regional policy makers, private sector companies, and other relevant stakeholders to collaboratively discuss study findings and refine recommendations regarding how USAID/RDMA can support regional SCR.

The workshop will begin with an overview of the findings and conclusions related to each assessment question. The findings and conclusions will be shared in advance, so that the participants have an opportunity to separately reflect on them prior to working through a shared understanding of the conclusions in a group setting and proposed recommendations.

This workshop will enable the AT and stakeholders to co-create recommendations based on the findings and conclusions, prior to submission of the draft report. The TL, Project Director (PD), and a Facilitation Expert will facilitate this discussion to ensure strong linkages among the findings, conclusions, and recommendations so each recommendation is well supported by evidence.

Although the workshops will not result in the full set of recommendations that appear in the assessment report, they will be an important step toward generating buy-in for the recommendations and ensuring that the recommendations are feasible and actionable.

The AT and USAID will work collaboratively to set the agenda, participant list, and materials for the proposed half-day virtual workshop.

FINAL REPORT

The study report will answer all assessment questions and sub-questions and will make clear how the questions were answered. Following receipt of USAID feedback, the AT will document and address each comment, using these to produce a fully compliant and high-quality final version of the USAID/RDMA SCR Deep Dive Final Report. The report will be submitted in both Microsoft Word with tracked changes and Adobe PDF as the polished version and uploaded to the DEC upon USAID/RDMA approval and according to the terms and conditions of the contract. The final evaluation report will contain only aggregated data and not refer explicitly to responses collected from any of the stakeholders or contacts interviewed during the study.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The AT upholds respect for each participant and understands that they must be free to participate in the study or not of their own accord and can cease their participation at any time. The interviewer must show their respect, ability to listen, and empathy throughout all interviews. Participants must be informed of the nature of their participation as well as any risks and benefits associated with their participation through an informed consent process prior to the interview.

The AT will need official letters from USAID for the assessment introduction and to request cooperation from all key informants. Prior to each interview every key informant will receive an email including the official introductory letter and consent form (see **Annex 4** for the informed consent). At the beginning of each interview, the team will review the consent form again and obtain verbal agreement for their participation and to record the interview

LIMITATIONS AND BIASES

BIASES AND MITIGATION STRATEGIES

The AT is aware of several bias risks in data collection and analysis and proposes strategies to mitigate them. To overcome potential biases generally, the AT will conduct as many KIIs as possible within the fieldwork period and available resources to triangulate responses and increase the validity and reliability of the findings. The AT will also use clear consent scripts that emphasize confidentiality and the volunteer nature, of the data collection. Two noteworthy bias risks in data collection and analysis include:

- **Response Bias:** Response bias is the risk that key informants may be motivated to provide responses that would be considered socially desirable or influential in obtaining donor support.

Response bias, which is connected to cultural and social norms, may also be affected by gender and social ranking. If the first person who speaks in a group discussion is the most senior, other participants might take their cues from that person and only echo his/her responses. The AT will mitigate this risk by:

- Minimizing, to the extent possible, the connection between the assessment and any future opportunities for support in the consent script the team will administer before each KII.
- **Gender Bias:** Gender bias is a risk because most individuals have a subconscious sense of appropriate roles and behavior for women and men. The AT will review gender-sensitive approaches during the inception period, focusing discussion on what possible gender preconceptions might come into play during this assessment, and reviewing how to minimize these during data collection and analysis.

LIMITATIONS AND MITIGATION STRATEGIES

The AT realizes that SCR has widespread implications for many types of stakeholders across a vast territory that is represented by Southeast Asian countries. The numbers of institutions/ organizations affected by SCR are too numerous to cover entirely in this assessment. The AT will mitigate this limitation by bringing together diverse groups of stakeholders to obtain varied responses that will capture current regional thinking about SCR.

The AT also realizes that some KII participants might not be conversant in certain languages used during the interviews. The AT will ensure that at least one member of the team can communicate in the language of the key informant(s), if needed. Each session will be recorded and made available for translation.

The AT will mitigate data quality risks, wherever possible, by collecting data from varied sources and triangulated responses to corroborate findings. To ensure the data quality, the team will conduct comprehensive qualitative data collection training, participate in interviews during the entire duration of data collection, revising protocols as needed, and provide continuous oversight via regular debriefs, if necessary, with other team members. The team will highlight any limitations that cannot be effectively mitigated in the report.

QUALITY ASSURANCE

Social Impact will apply its innovative Ensure Quality, Utilization, and Impact (EQUI®) quality assurance process to all aspects of this assessment. This approach ensures that all final deliverables are high quality, influential, and enhance development effectiveness. Developed over ten years through hundreds of evaluations and assessments in over 85 countries, EQUI® has proven effective in driving exceptional learning, accountability, and performance improvement.

By following utilization-focused evaluation principles, SI ensures all evaluations and assessments engage key users and are clearly targeted to their decision-making needs. To achieve maximum relevance to stakeholders and maintain the highest possible technical quality, EQUI® employs rigorous Quality Assurance checkpoints at key stages of the assessment. This system will ensure that the information generated by this assessment is useful and utilizable for the principal stakeholders within USAID/RDMA and beyond.

STUDY DESIGN MATRIX

The Study design Matrix below links the study question to the data collection methods, data sources, and the analysis methods. **Annex 5** includes data collection instruments, organized by the AQs and the stakeholder type.

Table 2: Study Design Matrix

Study Question	Data Collection Method	Data Sources	Illustrative Tool	Analysis Methods
<p>AQ1</p> <p>What are the main challenges to regional SCR in SEA given ongoing and probable future shocks in SEA?</p>	<p>Desk review</p> <p>KIIs</p>	<p>Secondary sources: journals, reports, magazines</p> <p>Primary sources: Individuals at multilateral, government institutions, regional organizations, and associations executives at companies, academicians at universities and think tanks</p>	<p>KII Semi-structured questionnaires</p>	<p>Comparative analysis</p> <p>Content analysis</p> <p>GESI analysis (marginalized groups)</p>
<p>AQ2</p> <p>What public and private actors are working regionally to identify and mitigate SCR risks and vulnerabilities?</p>	<p>Desk review</p> <p>KIIs</p>	<p>Secondary sources: Journals, reports, magazines</p> <p>Primary sources: individuals at multilateral/government institutions, regional organizations, associations, executives at companies, academicians at universities, think tanks</p>	<p>KII Semi-structured questionnaire</p>	<p>Comparative analysis</p> <p>Content analysis</p> <p>Thematic analysis</p>
<p>AQ2a</p> <p>Which economic sectors offer the best opportunities to bolster regional SCR in SEA in a way that</p>	<p>Desk review</p> <p>KII</p>	<p>Secondary sources: Journals, reports, magazines</p> <p>Primary sources: individuals at multilateral</p>	<p>KII semi-structured questionnaires</p>	<p>Comparative analysis</p> <p>Content analysis</p> <p>Thematic analysis</p>

Study Question	Data Collection Method	Data Sources	Illustrative Tool	Analysis Methods
can serve as a model for other sectors?		/government institutions, regional organizations, associations, executives at companies, academicians at universities, think tanks		Quantitative analysis
AQ2b. How can these actors be supported?	Desk review Klls	Secondary sources: Journals, reports, magazines Primary sources: individuals at multilateral /government institutions, regional organizations, associations, executives at companies, academicians at universities, think tanks	Kll Semi-structured questionnaire	Comparative analysis Content analysis Thematic analysis
AQ3 What are potential frameworks that USAID could employ to monitor SCR risks?	Desk review Klls	Secondary sources: Journals, reports, magazines Primary sources: individuals at multilateral /government institutions, regional organizations, associations, executives at companies, academicians at universities, think tanks	Kll semi-structured questionnaire	Comparative analysis Content analysis

TIMELINE OF DELIVERABLES

Table 3: Timeline of Deliverables

Phase I: Workplan and Design Phase	Organization	Tentative Dates
Draft Inception Report/Work Plan to USAID	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
• [Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
Final Inception Report/Work Plan to USAID	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
• [Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
Phase II: Data Collection and Out brief		
Data collection (virtual)	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
Preliminary Findings Presentation to USAID	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
Phase III: Data Analysis and Reporting		
Information Dissemination Workshop	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
Draft Assessment Report to USAID	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
• [Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
Final Assessment Report to USAID	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
• [Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

*Note: If there are further comments from USAID on the final version of the report, the tentative timelines for the submission of [Redacted]

ANNEXES

ANNEX I: TIMELINE

Table 4: Assessment Workplan Timeline

Phase	Task	20-Sep	27-Sep	4-Oct	11-Oct	18-Oct	25-Oct	1-Nov	8-Nov	15-Nov	22-Nov	29-Nov	6-Dec	13-Dec	20-Dec	27-Dec	3-Jan	10-Jan	17-Jan
Phase 0	Task 1	█																	
	Task 2		█	█															
Phase I: Workplan and Design	Task 3				█	█													
	Task 4						█	█	█										
	Task 5								█										
	Task 6								█	█	█								
	Task 7											█							
	Task 8													█					
Task 3: Data Collection and Analysis	Task 9									█	█								
	Task 10												█						
	Task 11											█	█						
	Task 12												█						

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ANNEX 3: ILLUSTRATIVE LIST OF KEY STAKEHOLDERS³⁷

Table 5 List of Key Informants

Stakeholder Type		Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
Business Associations CSOs	Business Councils/ Associations	EU ASEAN Business Council (Singapore)	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Singapore
		ASEAN Business Advisory Council	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Thailand
		APEC Business Advisory Council	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	
		US ASEAN Business Council (offices across ASEAN, Singapore)	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Singapore
		Trans-Atlantic Business Council (Washington)	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Washington
		Vietnam Association for Supporting Industries (VASI) and other industry Associations	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Hanoi, Vietnam

³⁷ Note these are informants the AT will attempt to interview, but the final interviewees will depend on whether respondents are available and willing to be interviewed. The AT targets completing between 70 to 78 interviews.

Stakeholder Type	Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone	
		Global Supply Chain Council	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	HK
		Asia Business Council	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	TBD
		National logistics industry associations	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	HoChiMinh City
	Academia / Thinktanks	ERIA	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	
		CARI	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Malaysia
		ISEAS - Yusof Ishak Institute	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	TBD
		ADB	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Manila

Stakeholder Type		Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
		Asia Society	TBD	TBD	Jakarta
		ASIA Foundation	TBD	TBD	Thailand/ Indonesia
		CIEM (Central Institute of Economic Management - Vietnam)	TBD	TBD	Hanoi, Vietnam
		National University of Singapore	TBD	TBD	Singapore
	Bi-lateral Chambers of Commerce	AmCham Singapore	TBD	TBD	Singapore
		AmCham in Vietnam	TBD	TBD	Hanoi, Vietnam
		AmCham Thailand	TBD	TBD	BKK, Thailand
		AmCham Cambodia	TBD	TBD	PhnomPenh
		EuroCham in Vietnam	TBD	TBD	Hanoi, Vietnam
		EuroCham Cambodia	TBD	TBD	PhnomPenh
		EuroCham Laos (ECCIAL)	TBD	TBD	Vientiane, Laos
	European Associations for Business and Commerce	TBD	TBD	BKK, Thailand	
		Laos	TBD	TBD	Vientiane, Laos

Stakeholder Type		Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
	National / Federal Chambers of Commerce	Thailand	TBD	TBD	BKK, Thailand
		Singapore	TBD	TBD	Singapore
		Cambodia	TBD	TBD	PhnomPenh
	US Associations	American Association of Importers and Exporters	TBD	TBD	Washington
	Agriculture/ Food	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
	Health	Pharmaceutical, Medical services and Devices	TBD	██████████	Singapore
	Hospitality and Tourism	Hotels, Airlines, Food and Beverages, Tour Operators	TBD	██████████	ASEAN
	Logistics companies	DHL	TBD	TBD	ASEAN
	Logistics companies	FedEx	TBD	██████████	Singapore

Stakeholder Type		Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
	Logistics companies	Logistics ICD at Vinh Phuc (Vietnam), a joint venture of T&T Vietnam with YCH Holdings (Singapore) and YCH Group Pte Ltd	TBD	[REDACTED]	Vinh Phuc, Vietnam
	Shipping	Maersk	TBD	[REDACTED]	Singapore
	Port Authorities	Singapore	TBD	[REDACTED]	Singapore
	Port Authorities	Malaysia	TBD	[REDACTED]	Malaysia
	Tech firms (Infrastructure, Services)	TBD	TBD	[REDACTED]	ASEAN
	Trade Finance/Banks	TBD	TBD	[REDACTED]	ASEAN
	Insurance	TBD	TBD	[REDACTED]	ASEAN
	US Firms in SEA	Ford	TBD	[REDACTED]	ASEAN
	US Firms in SEA	Apple	TBD	[REDACTED]	ASEAN

Stakeholder Type		Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
	US Firms in SEA	Intel	TBD	████	ASEAN
	EU firms in SE Asia	Daimler	TBD	██████████	Singapore
	EU firms in SE Asia	BMW	TBD	██████████	Singapore
	EU firms in SE Asia	Bosch	TBD	██████████	Singapore
	EU firms in SE Asia	Siemens	TBD	██████████	Singapore
	Japanese Firms in SE Asia	Toyota Singapore/ Vietnam	TBD	██████████	Singapore
	Japanese Firms in SE Asia	Canon Singapore/ Vietnam	TBD	██████████	Singapore
	Korean Firms in SE Asia	Samsung Singapore/ Vietnam	TBD	██████████	Singapore

Stakeholder Type		Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
	Regional Consulting Firms in SCR	PwC (Survey in March 2021)	TBD	[REDACTED]	Singapore
	Regional Consulting Firms in SCR	McKinsey	TBD	[REDACTED]	Singapore
	SMEs	TBD	TBD	TBD	
	Agriculture/ Food	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
	Media	Jakarta Post/ South China Morning Post	TBD	TBD	HK
	Media	The Economist February Editorial	TBD	[REDACTED]	Singapore
	WBG	World Bank (East Asia and Pacific)	TBD	TBD	TBD
	WBG	IFC	TBD	TBD	TBD
	ASEAN Plus Three (China+ Korea + Japan)	Japan	[REDACTED]	TBD	Japan

Stakeholder Type	Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
	China	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	China
	Korea	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Korea
	UK Mission to ASEAN (Indonesia based)	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Indonesia
	GIZ Laos/ Cambodia	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Laos
	EU Delegation in Bangkok	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Singapore
	EU Delegation in Singapore	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Singapore

Stakeholder Type		Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
		US Mission to ASEAN	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Jakarta
Government/ Intergovernmental	Asia Pacific Economic Community	APEC Secretariat	TBD	TBD	Singapore
	ASEAN	ASEAN Economic Ministers/ SEOM	TBD	TBD	ASEAN
	ASEAN Secretariat Divisions	Trade Facilitation	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Indonesia WIB
	ASEAN Secretariat Divisions	Standards and Conformance	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Indonesia WIB
	ASEAN Secretariat Divisions	Services and Investment	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Indonesia WIB
	ASEAN Secretariat Divisions	SMEs	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Indonesia WIB

Stakeholder Type		Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
	ASEAN Secretariat Divisions	Competition and Consumer Protection	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Indonesia WIB
	ASEAN Secretariat Divisions	ASEAN Integration Monitoring Directorate	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Indonesia WIB
	ASEAN Sector Bodies and Working Groups	ACCSQ, ACCSME, AEGC	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	Indonesia WIB
	Initiatives Under the Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025,	SEOM (Senior Economic Officials Meeting)	[REDACTED]	[REDACTED]	ASEAN

Stakeholder Type		Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
	Initiatives Under the Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025,	STOM (Senior Transport Officials Meeting)	TBD		ASEAN
	Initiatives Under the Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025,	Customs DGs	TBD	TBD	ASEAN
	Initiatives Under the Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025,	DGICM (Directors-General of Immigration Departments and Heads of Consular Affairs Divisions of the Ministries of Foreign Affairs)	TBD	TBD	ASEAN
	Initiatives Under the Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025,	SOMHD (Senior Officials Meeting on Health Development)	TBD	TBD	ASEAN

Stakeholder Type		Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
	Initiatives Under the Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025,	Senior Officials Meeting for ASEAN Ministers on Agriculture and Forestry (SOM-AMAF)	TBD	████████████████████	ASEAN
	Initiatives Under the Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025,	Logistics and Transport Services Sectoral Working Group (LTSSWG)	TBD	████████████████████	ASEAN
	Initiatives Under the Master Plan on ASEAN Connectivity 2025,	Logistics coordinating councils	TBD	TBD	ASEAN
	Ministry of Industry and Trade (Vietnam)	Vietrade (Vietnam Trade Promotion Agency)	TBD	TBD	Hanoi, Vietnam

Stakeholder Type		Organization	Title of Key Informant	Name of Key Informant	Location/Time zone
	Ministry of Planning and Investment (Vietnam)	Agency of Enterprise Development (AED)	TBD	TBD	Hanoi, Vietnam
	Trade Support Organizations	Korea, (KOTRADE)	TBD	TBD	TBD
		Malaysia (MATRADE)	TBD	TBD	TBD
		KOTRA (Vietnam)	TBD	TBD	Hanoi, Vietnam
		JETRO (Japan External Trade Organization)	TBD	TBD	Hanoi, Vietnam

ANNEX 4: INFORMED CONSENTS

KII Consent

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Do you understand that your participation in this interview is voluntary, unpaid, and that you can end the interview at any point?

- Yes
- No

Do you confirm your consent to participate in this interview?

- Yes
- No

Do you confirm your consent for this interview to be recorded?

- Yes
- No

ANNEX 5: DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS

Private Sector KII Questions

Instructions for Interviewers

- This audience is likely to operate in specific sectors and industries, allowing for insights to emerge thematically around sectors.
- Key Informants selected are
 - Large, multinational organizations, academia, CSOs/BSOs and SMEs operating in SEA (or at least representing those interests) we can, therefore, assume that they have been impacted by SC shocks such as COVID-19 at the very least and have had significant exposure to SC disruption exposure and will have insights to contribute to enhancing SCR in SEA.
- As COVID-19 is the most recent large scale, unanticipated disruption, this will be used to ground the questions and gather insights.
- Interviewer should ground the respondent in the research enquiry and ensure that key terms such as SC Risk, SC Vulnerability, and SC Resilience are explained, to ensure consistency of responses.
- All data collection tools will include the consent script.

Section I: What are the main challenges to regional SCR in SEA given ongoing and probable future shocks in SEA?

- Can you please tell us briefly about the sector you operate in?
 - Categorization options: Firm descriptor, business association remit etc. [some key information about the organization/interviewer should be prepared in advance by the interviewer/AT to make the interview informative and add more valuable data that could not be possible without the interview].
- Which do you think are the supply chain risks that will have the most impact on your sector? (AQ 1 and 2)
 - What approaches do you think exist to better understand the risks and impact?
 - What steps are you currently taking to mitigate the challenges and develop awareness of the vulnerabilities to emerging types of SC risk?
 - Specifically, on improving knowledge to enhance awareness of the vulnerabilities and the challenges they pose?
 - Question prompts:
 - Environmental – natural disasters, extreme weather, pandemics.
 - Energy/Infrastructure – access to energy supplies, energy costs, capacity of ports, roads, logistics providers.
 - Geopolitical – conflicts and war, export/import restrictions, terrorism etc.
 - Political – civil unrest, embargo, blockage.
 - Economic – sudden demand shocks, prices, border delays, financial crisis, currency, labor etc.
 - Technical – information and comms disruption, transport infrastructure failure.
 -
 - Can you describe any SCR early warning measures that you had in place prior to 2020?
 - To what extent and in what ways, do you rely on media coverage in the general news media or industry publications for information about emerging SC risks?

- Beyond the media, what specific channels, forums and/or networks do you use to help you understand and plan for SC risks on a regular basis?
- How did you become aware of SC risks and impacts such as the COVID-19 pandemic and other potential crises in your sector's SC?
- What steps did you take in the immediate term to respond to the SC disruptions resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic?
- How do you think these actions will affect different populations that you employ, work with, or serve? Are there considerations for specific sections of the population who are disproportionately negatively affected such as migrant workers, women, youth, ethnic minorities, disabled persons etc.

Section 2 (AQ 2): What public and private actors are working regionally to identify and mitigate SCR risks and vulnerabilities? Which economic sectors offer the opportunities to bolster regional SCR in SEA in a way that can serve as a model for other sectors? (AQ 2)

- In your view, what kind of responses have most helped SC recovery from the pandemic?
 - From government side, what policies have helped? Which policies have become barriers and had negative impacts? What could they have done differently? What can they do in the future? What policies can help reduce the negative impacts on marginalized groups? Which organizations/institutions could be in charge and were most active/helpful in responding to SC recovery? (AQ 2) Helpful to men/women?
 - [Firms] Did you receive any advice, support, concessions from upstream or downstream suppliers? Which organizations were most helpful in responding to SC recovery? Which, if any, organizations that work specifically with marginalized people within SCs should/could have been included? Which organizations could or should have been more engaged in fostering SC recovery? (AQ 2)
 - [Business associations] what kind of requests did you get for assistance from firms to help them with SC recovery? Were any of those requests something that you couldn't help with but you think organizations like yours should be able to help address? (AQ 2)
- [Business associations] Given your insights on SC recovery processes in SEA and your sector, what are key economic sectors that need to be prioritized to allow SEA SC to function at optimal performance? (AQ 2)
- [Business associations] Which sectors do you think have best responded to SC recovery process and why do you think this was so? How could this be replicated in your sector or modelled to other sectors in SEA? (AQ 2) Any differences in outcomes between men or women owned SMEs? (AQ 2)
- [Firms] What learnings do you have about the SC recovery process in your sector? What insights can you draw from related firms operating in your sector in other parts of the world? Were there useful interventions above the firm level such as competitors or sector groups working together? How will this inform strategies in your sector? (AQ 2)

Section 3 (AQ 2): What public and private actors are active in identifying and addressing regional supply chain vulnerabilities? How can these actors be supported? (AQ 3)

- From the public sector (incl. government, academia, NGOs, civil society etc.), which organizations and/or institutions have provided the most effective support in helping you to identify and address regional SC vulnerabilities?

- What kind of support was offered? E.g., policy aid, technical assistance etc.
- Who were the intended beneficiaries? To what extent did these include any marginalized groups like migrant workers or displaced people?
- What, if any, gaps were there in their support?
- How do you think the public sector support could have been improved?
- From the private sector (business associations, other firms, upstream and downstream suppliers, consultancy firms etc.), which organizations or institutions have provided what type of support and which have been the most effective in helping you to identify and address regional SC vulnerabilities? (AQ 3)
 - What kind of support was offered or procured by these organizations? E.g., business associations, management consultancy etc.
 - Which were most effective
 - What was accomplished with the support?
 - Were there any gaps in their support? If so, what do you think they were?
 - How do you think they can be supported to improve the support they provided, or could provide better?
- How would you mitigate future shocks to SCs in your sector? (AQ 3)
 - How do you think your sector should invest resources to better understand emergent large scale SC risks?
 - What options do you have to mitigate impacts on SC vulnerabilities, to enhance SCR in your sector? And how would you evaluate the potential success of these options?
 - What options do other players in your sector have to mitigate impacts on SC vulnerabilities, and/or to enhance SCR in your sector that are outside of your control? How can other support you? And how do you evaluate these options?
 - If you had \$100,000 to invest in SCR, how would you allocate this investment to: monitor risks, detect vulnerabilities, define strategies to mitigate against vulnerabilities, leverage resources outside of your firm/sector to exert control on systemic vulnerabilities? (AQ 2b)
 - How can local economic agents (such as workers, managers, owners) and member states (at country level) protect economic actors from marginalized groups such as female entrepreneurs or migrant workers from supply chain shocks? Are there policies that would help make supply chains more inclusive?

Section 4: What are the potential frameworks that USAID can employ to monitor SCR? (AQ 3)

- To support private sector efforts to promote SC resilience in SEA, how can USAID leverage policy development and advocacy efforts? [Use the below questions as prompts – this can be open ended to see how others see USAID supporting, but it’s too broad to focus the main Research Question]. (AQ 3)
- Knowledge development (AQ 3)
 - Given the discussion above [from the first interview question], what knowledge areas do you think USAID should prioritize to enhance awareness of SC risks, its impacts and ability of SEA SC to recover (SCR)?
 - What type of information is most effective in supporting SCR at a sectoral level, and/or at the firm level? Policy reports, sectoral findings, scientific findings from academia, management consultancy, information and insights arising from regional databases?
- Knowledge sharing (AQ 4)
 - What kind of information do you think is critical to be shared within your sector to promote SCR?

- What kind of information do you think is important to be shared for SCR despite the risk that it may be controversial e.g., for commercial confidentiality, intellectual property, data protection or for other reasons?
- What kind of information platforms have been most effective to support SCR? For women, migrant workers, ethnic groups, youth?
- Which platforms are least effective? For women, migrant workers, ethnic groups, youth?
- What alternative SCR platforms would you recommend for open knowledge sharing? For women, migrant workers, ethnic groups, youth?
- Do any platforms that already work with local actors might overlap with those used with marginalized groups?
- Network strengthening (AQ 3)
 - What type of networks or forums are already participating in discussions on SCR?
 - To what networks/organizations would you like access to but don't?
 - Why would you like access to these?
 - What do you think they can provide that you do not already have access to?
 - Given the above discussion, which kind of stakeholders would you say are essential to have in discussions on SCR? What group (s) should be involved?
 - If there is sensitive information to be shared to support SCR, who should be in these groups?
 - What, if any, principles do you think they should adhere to?

Public Sector KIIs Questions

Instructions for Interviewers

This audience is likely to have knowledge of specific sectors and industries, allowing for insights to emerge thematically around sectors.

- Key Informants selected are
 - National Governments and Development Agencies and Regional Organizations operating in regulatory, policy and investment areas in SEA (or at least affecting those interests) we can therefore, assume that they have responded to the COVID-19 impacts and have had significant exposure to SC realities and disruption and will have insights to contribute to enhancing SCR in SEA.
- As COVID-19 is the most recent large scale, un-anticipated disruption, this will be used to ground the questions and gather insights.
- Interviewer should ground the respondent in the research enquiry and ensure that key terms such as SC Risk, SC Vulnerability, SC Resilience and SC Recovery are explained, to ensure consistency of responses.
- All data collection tools will include the consent script.

Section I: What are the main challenges to regional SCR in SEA given ongoing and probable future shocks in SEA?

- Can you please tell us briefly about your organization and the sector that you operate in?
 - Categorization options: Firm descriptor, business association remit etc.
- What do you think are the next set of global supply chain risks that are likely to have the most impact? (AQ1)
 - What approaches do you think exist are the best to understand the risks and impact?
 - What steps are you currently taking to develop awareness of the vulnerabilities to different types of SC risk? (AQ 1)

- Rank from 1-4 your awareness (1=not aware, 2=slightly aware, 3=moderately aware, 4=very aware) your confidence in your awareness of the vulnerabilities? (AQ 1)
 - Question prompts:
 - Environmental – natural disasters, extreme weather, pandemics.
 - Energy/Infrastructure – access to energy supplies, energy costs, capacity of ports, roads, logistics providers.
 - Geopolitical – conflicts and war, export/import restrictions, terrorism etc.
 - Political – civil unrest.
 - Economic – sudden demand shocks, prices, border delays, currency, labor etc.
 - Technical – information and comms disruption, transport infrastructure failure.
 - Why do you perceive it this way i.e why do you think you have low or high awareness of the specific areas?
- At what point were you aware of the risks and impact of SC risks such as the COVID-19 pandemic on your sector's SC? (AQ 1 and AQ 2)
- Beyond the media, what specific channels, forum or network did you use to help you understand and plan for the COVID-19 and other SC negative impacts, in the immediate term? (AQ 1 and AQ 2)
- What steps did you take to respond to and support the SC disruptions, in the immediate term? (AQ 1 and AQ 2)

Section 2 (AQ 2): What public and private actors are working regionally to identify and mitigate SCR risks and vulnerabilities? Which economic sectors offer the opportunities to bolster regional SCR in SEA in a way that can serve as a model for other sectors? (AQ 2a)

- In your view, what kind of responses have most helped SC recovery from the pandemic?
 - From the government side, what policies have helped. Which policies have had a negative impact? What could they have done differently? What can they do in the future? Which organizations/institutions were most helpful in responding to SC recovery?
 - Regarding firms, did you receive any requests, advice, support, any concession from upstream or downstream suppliers? Which organizations were most helpful in responding to SC recovery? Which, if any, organizations that work specifically with marginalized people within SCs should/could have been included? (AQ 2)
 - Regarding business associations, what kind of requests did you get for assistance for sectors to help with SC recovery? Any differences in the types of requests between men or women owned SMEs? (AQ 2)
- Given your insights on SC recovery processes in SEA and in your sector, what are key economic sectors that need to be prioritized to allow SEA SC to function at optimal performance? ? (AQ 2a)
- Which sectors do you think have best responded to SC recovery process and why do you think this was so? Can this be replicated in your sector or other sectors in SEA? (AQ2a)
- What learnings do you have from firms about the SC recovery process in your sector? What insights can you draw from firms operating in your area in other parts of the world? How will this inform your future strategies? (AQ 2a)

Section 3 (AQ 2 and AQ 2b): What public and private actors are active in identifying and addressing regional supply chain vulnerabilities (AQ 2)? How can these actors be supported? (AQ 2b)

- Which public sector organizations or institutions have provided the most effective ideas for support in helping to identify and address regional SC vulnerabilities?
 - How did you collaborate?
 - What kind of support was offered? E.g., policy, aid, technical assistance etc.
 - Were there any gaps in your/ their support? If so, what do you think they were?
 - How do you think they can be supported to improve the support you/ they provided, or could provide better?
- From the private sector (business associations, other firms, upstream and downstream suppliers, consultancy firms etc.), which organizations or institutions have provided the most effective support in helping you to identify and address regional SC vulnerabilities?
 - What kind of support was offered or procured? E.g., management consultancy.
 - Were there any gaps in their support? If so, what do you think they were?
 - How do you think they can be supported to improve the support they provided, or could provide better?
- How would you mitigate future shocks to SCs in your area of purview? (AQ 2)
 - How would you invest public/ private and joint resources to better understand emergent large scale SC risks?
 - What options do you have to mitigate impacts on SC vulnerabilities, to enhance SCR in areas under your purview?
 - If you had \$100,000 to invest in SCR, how would you allocate this investment to: monitor risks, detect vulnerabilities, define strategies to mitigate against vulnerabilities, leverage resources outside of your firm/sector to exert control on systemic vulnerabilities? (AQ 2b)
 - How can local economic agents (such as workers, managers, owners) and member states (at country level) protect economic actors from marginalized groups such as female entrepreneurs or migrant workers from supply chain shocks? Are there policies that would help make supply chains more inclusive?

Section 4: What are the potential frameworks that USAID can employ to monitor SCR? (AQ 3)

- To support private sector efforts to promote SC resilience in SEA, how can USAID leverage policy development and advocacy efforts? [Use the below questions as prompts – this in itself can be open ended to see how others see USAID supporting, but it's too broad to focus the main Research Question]. (AQ 3)
 - Knowledge development (AQ 3)
 - Given the discussion above [from the first interview question], what knowledge areas do you think USAID should prioritize to enhance awareness of SC risks, its impacts and ability of SEA SC to recover (SCR)?
 - What type of information is most effective in supporting SCR? Policy reports, sectoral findings, scientific findings from academia, management consultancy, information and insights arising from regional databases?
 - Knowledge sharing (AQ3)
 - What kind of information do you think is critical to be shared within your sector to promote SCR?

- What kind of information do you think is important to be shared for SCR but may be controversial e.g., for commercial confidentiality, intellectual property, data protection or for other reasons?
 - What kind of information platforms have been most effective for you to support SCR? For women, migrant workers, ethnic groups, youth?
 - Which platforms are least effective? For women, migrant workers, ethnic groups, youth?
 - Would you recommend alternative SCR platforms for open knowledge sharing? For women, migrant workers, ethnic groups, youth?
 - Do any platforms that already work with local actors might overlap with those used with marginalized groups?
- Network strengthening (AQ3)
 - What type of networks or forums are you already participating in to discuss SCR?
 - Are there networks/organizations that you would like access to but do not have?
 - Why would you like access to these?
 - What do you think they can provide which you do not already have access to?
 - Given the above discussion, which kind of stakeholders would you say are essential to have in discussions on SCR? Women? Youth? Migrant workers? Disabled persons? Ethnic groups?
 - If there is sensitive information to be shared to support SCR, who should be in these groups?
 - Are there any principles you think they should adhere to?

ANNEX 6: SCOPE OF WORK

I. INTRODUCTION

This Deep Dive would identify specific findings and recommendations for USAID RDMA to explore its potential role in strengthening the resilience of Asia-Pacific regional supply chains.

II. BACKGROUND

Since the late 1960s, SEA has been steadily moving towards greater regional integration. Regional economic integration has allowed individual countries and the overall region to position themselves as major players in the global economy. However, economic integration with global markets had the side-effect of making the region one of the most vulnerable to the kinds of environmental, economic, and health-related shocks that create major disruptions in supply chains. The ongoing COVID-19 pandemic and its negative impacts on virtually all sectors is just one illustration of how economic integration can amplify certain risks. The Indo-Pacific region faces challenges, such as unsustainable debt levels, digital transformation needs, and collapsing supply and value chains; all of this has been exacerbated by COVID-19. Regarding global value chains, COVID-19 has also exposed weaknesses, such as an overreliance on production in the PRC, that further impacts hard-hit economies.

As regional bodies prioritize supply chain diversification and economic cooperation to help mitigate vulnerability to these shocks, RDMA will closely coordinate with other regional actors, such as ASEAN, around shared policy objectives towards economic connectivity.

Concern over the threat of these economic, political, environmental, and health shocks continue to reshape how regional economies operate and develop. For example, months after COVID-19 was first reported, the long-term ripple effects of the pandemic continue to reverberate throughout all sectors. The Regional J2SR Landscape Analysis suggests lower than average scores for export sophistication in Southeast Asia which contributes to lower economic resilience. A primary driver of this is overreliance on single supply sources for goods within the region, which increases exposure to shocks—as evidenced during the COVID-19 pandemic—and further complicates economic recovery. These exposed supply-side vulnerabilities have been disproportionately affecting small and medium-sized enterprises, especially in Least Developed Countries in the region. As evidenced in the COVID-19 recovery, successful businesses were those with diverse supply sources, allowing them to pivot and ensure a steady base of available goods. This can and has created new benefits for other countries in the region and will create new investment opportunities.

Regional Development Objective 2 (RDO2) of the USAID/RDMA's Regional Development Cooperation Strategy for Asia (2020–2025) will address these supply vulnerabilities by strengthening regional supply chains to become more resilient to unanticipated, long-term shocks like COVID-19. Furthermore, by supporting sustainable, reliable, and secure supply chains that adhere to green growth strategies, RDO 2 will complement RDO 3 efforts. Supporting RDO 4, secure and reliable data management is key for strengthening regional health networks. Reliable and timely supply of healthcare products, including personal protective equipment, is even more of a priority as the region experiences more and more health shocks.

III. PURPOSE

The Supply Chain Resiliency Deep Dive will inform activity design and provide data for evidence-based decision making and identify possible approaches that benefit future USAID RDMA involvement and/or economic growth programming. The impacts and opportunities presented by the COVID-19 pandemic will be integrated into report findings. Test the logic of the causal statement:

“IF RDMA supports policy development and advocacy efforts that a) support private sector efforts to promote supply chain resiliency, and b) reduce barriers to using open platforms for knowledge-sharing and network strengthening, THEN RDMA can effectively help supply chains in the region be more resilient to unanticipated, long-term shocks.”

The Supply Chain Resiliency Deep Dive calls for the completion of two interconnected tasks:

- An analysis of data and information on priority entry points, including policymaking bodies and private sector networks around vulnerabilities among regional supply chains; and
- The co-development of an information dissemination workshop that includes recommendations for programmatic approaches to work with public and private platforms to advance supply chain resiliency at a regional level.

IV. KEY ASSESSMENT QUESTIONS

The Supply Chain Resiliency Deep Dive will provide a detailed understanding of the following questions:

- What are the main challenges to regional SCR in SEA given ongoing and probable future shocks in SEA?
 - What are the probable future shocks expected?
- What public and private actors are working regionally to identify and mitigate SCR risks and vulnerabilities?
 - Which economic sectors offer the best opportunities to bolster regional SCR in SEA in a way that can serve as a model for other sectors?
 - How can these actors be supported?
- What are the potential frameworks USAID could employ to develop a regional early warning system that could help identify SCR risks that could help reduce the impact of supply chain disruptions?

V. ASSESSMENT DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

The contractor must propose the Assessment plan and methodology to answer the Assessment questions. USAID RDMA requires a participatory approach throughout the implementation of this assessment. The contractor must provide in its assessment work plan the rationale behind the methods selected, why they are appropriate, how they provide rigor to answering the questions, as well as how data quality will be assured.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

USAID requests that the contractor complete the following table as part of its detailed Assessment design. Please note that another format may be used if the table is not preferred, but any chosen format should contain all the information specified for each question.

Assessment question	Data Source	Data collection method and tool	Data analysis method

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In addition to responses to all assessment questions, the assessment will also center around developing recommendations that align with USAID’s current policies and priorities, including the Indo-Pacific Framework, the RDMA Regional Development Cooperation Strategy, USAID New Partnerships Initiative, J2SR, and to present findings to USAID. The Assessment will proceed as outlined below:

- Literature review, detailed design and work plan preparation, preliminary data collection tool development, logistics: Materials to review will include, but not be limited to:
 - Periodicals, studies, analyses, and papers that have been conducted to date, both public and gray literature.
 - Findings from COVID-19 related impact analyses.
 - Current USAID policies, strategies, and priorities, as well as those of RDMA as relevant.
- Data Collection and Initial Impressions Presentation: The Assessment team will gather data remotely from relevant stakeholders and experts from US Government, USAID, relevant government entities in the SEA region, civil society, private sector stakeholders, think tanks, academia, donors, and others. This will also include regular check-ins with USAID. The Assessment team will present initial impressions from their field work to the USAID team for validation and feedback.
- Information Dissemination Workshop: This one-day workshop will be held with USAID to present compiled responses to Assessment questions and illustrative recommendations. This workshop will be hosted virtually. The purpose will be to convene USAID bilateral mission staff and select informants who participated in data collection to discuss opportunities for USG engagement on supply chain resiliency.
- Wrap Up Summary Report Writing: Final compilation of analyzed data, inclusion of discussions/questions from Information Dissemination Workshop, and recommendations.

V. TEAM COMPOSITION AND REQUIRED EXPERTISE

[REDACTED]

VI. KEY DELIVERABLES

- [REDACTED]

VII. ESTIMATED TIMEFRAME

The estimated timeframe for the Assessment is from early [REDACTED]

VIII. ROLE OF THE USAID MISSION

- [REDACTED]

³⁸ To include relevant regional government entities, civil society organizations, and private sector associations.

